

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE TOWARDS ROLE STRESS AMONG INDIGENOUS SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 25 Dec 20023 Revised: 8 Jan 2024 Accepted: 25 Jan 2024 Published: 1 Feb 2024</p>	<p>In becoming a developed country, we must build a nation that can continuously think critically, innovatively, and creatively and be prepared to be knowledgeable and highly skilled workers for the country. In empowering the quality education system, teachers are strongly required to perform their responsibilities and roles respectively and accordingly. The teaching profession is indeed challenging. This situation, therefore, has opened up the space for teachers to be exposed to the issue of work pressure. Various efforts have been implemented to avoid and reduce stress among teachers and promote a healthy work and lifestyle. Empowering spiritual intelligence is one of the best and most accurate efforts in cultivating the ability to face challenges and further achieve each other's goals. Therefore, this study is conducted first to view the level of role stress and spiritual intelligence among indigenous school teachers. In addition, it also examined the level of relationship between spiritual intelligence and role stress among indigenous school teachers. The research design is quantitative, correlating with a cross-sectional survey method using a set of questionnaires on a sample of 110 indigenous school teachers. The descriptive data analysis technique is applied via the SPSS software version 27. The study's finding shows that the role stress level of the indigenous school teachers is moderately high (Mean=3.2636, S.P= .74046). However, the level of spiritual intelligence is high (Mean=4.1800, S.P= .43700). Based on the inference data analysis, it shows that there is a significant negative relationship between spiritual intelligence and role stress ($r = .0232, p < 0.05$). In conclusion, although it is only moderately high, this does not indicate any role stress. It still exists among teachers, but fortunately the situation is controlled and not worrying. However, ignoring and improperly managing this condition could lead to a more severe implication.</p>
<p>Keywords: Role stress, spiritual intelligence, teachers, indigenous schools</p> <p></p>	

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INTRODUCTION

The quality and civilization of a nation can be changed and influenced by an education system, which is one of the major agendas for a country. A nation is considered backward if it does not have a good education system. Education has become one of the main sectors in developing a country. Suppose a country aims to build a critical, innovative and creative nation who are ready to become knowledgeable and highly skilled workers for the country. In that case, it can only be achieved through a quality education system. As a result the nation can face and survive in this globalization era that is increasingly challenging and stressful. In empowering the quality education system, teachers are strongly required to perform their respective and stated responsibilities and roles. According to Azri Bhari (2022), the trust entrusted to teachers is not something easy; it requires seriousness and high purity to realize the country's hope to produce a civilized society. And indeed, the teaching profession is challenging. This situation has opened up the space for teachers to be exposed to work pressure issues. Teachers are also exposed to stress syndrome due to the high workload and continuous working time at school or home (Siti Azira Jose et al., 2021). This pressure can be a problem among teachers, which can eventually lead to anxiety and depression. This situation negatively impacts the teacher's health and risks their poor physical and mental well-being (Agyapong, 2022). All teachers should look after their mental well-being because stress can later affect their ability to manage classes, plan lessons, complete the curriculum, and affect the well-being of students and the school (Agarwal, 2022). Hans Selye formally introduced this concept of work pressure or stress in the 1930s. Selye's greatest contribution was in introducing a fundamental concept about stress-related diseases.

According to Premjani (2022), various efforts have been taken to avoid and reduce stress to promote a healthy lifestyle. Empowering spiritual intelligence is one of the best and most accurate efforts in cultivating the ability to face problems and further achieve each others' goals. In addition, spiritual intelligence is believed to assist individuals in improving their mental well-being, which is necessary to face stress (Irenne and Wisesa, 2020). Siti Mahannah (2020) also asserted that spiritual intelligence is a vital aspect of intelligence in determining energy in a person's work. Siadari (2020) defined spiritual intelligence as individuals' ability to solve every daily challenge.

In comparison to the context of Islam, spiritual intelligence means the ability of an individual to cleanse their soul from negative influences by understanding the meaning and purpose of life, maintaining relationships with God, The Creator (Allah), and with other people, performing religious and charitable practices and having a great soul (Ashshidieqy, 2018). Therefore, spiritual intelligence needs to be a priority in protecting oneself from experiencing pressure, as emphasized by Al-Rashidi (2022), who states that spiritual growth can be the basis for humans to live a better and more integrated life. Therefore, for this research, the researchers have developed the following research objectives;

- i. To identify the levels of role stress among indigenous school teachers
- ii. To identify and examine the level of spiritual intelligence among indigenous school teachers
- iii. To investigate the relationship between spiritual intelligence and role stress among indigenous school teachers

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on Lazarus's Stress Theory, stress refers to pressure, an unpleasant condition for an individual due to pressure from the environment (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Lazarus Stress Theory explains that there are three (3) forms of stress, namely stimulus, response and process. Stimulus is a situation that leads to stress stimulation in an individual. The stimulus that results in stress is caused by the pressure of the surrounding people that exceeds the individual's ability. For example, a person who always emphasizes perfection always wants to succeed; if the individual experiences failure, he will feel depressed (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Besides that, the response is an individual's reaction when a stressful situation occurs. When stress occurs, there are two types of response, which are physical response and psychological response. The physical response involves changes in behavior felt by the individual. For example, the heart will beat fast, sweat, and lose appetite.

In contrast, psychological response involves emotions such as depression, anxiety, negative thoughts, and difficulties in concentrating. Usually, physical and psychological responses are interrelated to each other when a person is in stress. These two responses are called strain or tension (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

According to Vickovic & Morrow (2019), work stress is a burden of life experienced by employees who do jobs that are not specific to themselves. If an employee is forced to do work beyond their field and ability, it may cause them not to be able to perform the job well. In addition, stress is a negative human reaction to social stimuli, work environment, insufficient reward, intense demands of lifestyle, and so on (Cyrill Frederick Ganing et al., 2020).

As an effort to promote a healthy lifestyle, many people tend to explore different ways to increase their resources and improve their abilities. An important aspect often empowered is spiritual intelligence, which functions in cultivating abilities that allow people to face problems and achieve their goals (Premjani, 2022). Spiritual intelligence assists a person in increasing their mental well-being, which is required in facing stress (Irenne & Wisesa, 2020; Khosravi & Nikmanesh, 2014; Koenig, 2010). According to Siadari (2020), spiritual intelligence is an individual's ability to solve every daily challenge. Finally, Al-Rashidi et al., (2022) affirmed that spiritual growth can be the basis for humans to live a better and more integrated life.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, the researchers have implemented a quantitative method in the form of a field study. This field method describes the ongoing nature of *exposed Facto* (causal effect) in the research, leading to accurate interpretation (Mohd Najib, 2003). Descriptive and inferential analysis is applied to analyze the research data to provide an overview of phenomena, show relationships, test hypotheses, make predictions, and obtain meaning from the implications of a problem to be solved (Sukarmin, 2010). Hypothesis testing is carried out to deeply investigate the relationship between variables – variables that have been assumed and then to answer the research questions (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013).

Sampling Design

In this study, the researchers have applied a simple random sampling method. This method was chosen based on the respondents' suitability and easiness of obtaining feedback and cooperation. This study involved former teacher trainees from Tengku Ampuan Afzan Teacher Education Campus, Kuala Lipis, Pahang, currently teaching in indigenous schools throughout Malaysia. They were selected to participate in this study at the initial stage to facilitate data collection as their number and placement can be obtained easily. Based on the enrollment/teacher data – the information on these teachers is obtained from The National Centre of Excellence for Indigenous Pedagogy (PKPPK). As for 2021, the total number of teachers is 112 teachers. However, only 110 questionnaires from the respondents were returned to be analyzed.

Instrument

A questionnaire is one form of instrument that was used in this research. According to Mohd Majid Konting (1990), respondents can easily, bravely and willingly respond to the aspects studied by using a questionnaire. Besides that, Mohd Najib Abd Ghafar (2003) stated that instruments in a well-constructed questionnaire could ease the researchers, and the data gathered will be easily processed and analyzed. In this study, the researchers prepared and administered an adapted questionnaire based on several relevant studies by other researchers in the same field. As the instrument used has met the aspects of validity and reliability, the content validity aspect has also been fulfilled (Sanchez-Franco & Roldán, 2010). The measurement for each construct is combined to form a research instrument, which consists of a questionnaire by Hu, Hu, and King (2017) to measure the construct of role stress. In addition, a questionnaire by Martin and John Hafer (2009) measures the construct of spiritual intelligence.

Data Collection Procedures

For this research, the data was collected through a questionnaire distributed online via a Google Form link. The questionnaire was designed by the researchers about the relevant literature, the conceptual framework that was compiled, as well as the purpose of the research.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic Profile of Respondents

In this research, the researchers implemented a descriptive statistical test method for the aspects related to the demographic profile of the respondents. Among the aspects that have been analyzed are the respondent's gender and field of teaching as shown in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Number of respondents by gender

		Respondents by gender			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	MALE	53	48.2	48.2	48.2
	FAMALE	57	51.8	51.8	100.0
	Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Based on Table 1.1, it shows that the total number of teachers involved in this study is 110 teachers. The number of female teachers is more than male teachers which is 57 (51.8%), whereas male teachers are 53 (48.2%).

Table 1.2. Number of respondents by field

		Respondents by Field			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	BM	18	16.4	16.4	16.4
	BI	16	14.5	14.5	30.9
	SN	14	12.7	12.7	43.6
	MT	21	19.1	19.1	62.7
	PI	6	5.5	5.5	68.2
	PJ	5	4.5	4.5	72.7
	MU	2	1.8	1.8	74.5
	Others	28	25.5	25.5	100.0
	Total	110	100.0	100.0	

The number of respondents according to the teaching field is shown in Table 1.2, and it shows that the field for 'Others' has more teachers, which is 28 teachers (25.5%). The field of 'Others' consists of Visual Arts Education, Moral Education, and History. In addition, 21 teachers are teaching Mathematics (19.1%), 18 teaching Bahasa Melayu (16.4%), and 16 teaching English (14.5%). Next, there are six teachers (5.5%) teaching Islamic Education, five teachers (4.5%) teaching Physical Education, and only two teachers teaching Music (1.8%).

Table 1.3. Mean value of role stress and spiritual intelligence

		Statistics	
		StresBSP	RohaniGKP
N	Valid	110	110
	Missing	0	0
Mean		3.2636	4.1800
Std. Deviation		.74046	.43700

Table 1.3 above shows that the level of role stress among indigenous school teachers is moderately high, while the level of spiritual intelligence is high. This is based on Table 1.4 Mean determination table.

Table 1.4. Mean Determination Table

Mean	Level
1.01 – 2.00	Low
2.01 – 3.00	Low Moderate
3.01 – 4.00	High Moderate
4.01 – 5.00	High

Sumber: Nunally, J.C. (1978) & Stufflebeam, D.L. (1973)

Inference Analysis

Table 1.5. Pearson correlation table

Correlations		StresBSP	RohaniGKP
StresBSP	Pearson Correlation	1	-.232*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015
	N	110	110
RohaniGKP	Pearson Correlation	-.232*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	
	N	110	110

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

To answer the third research question, Pearson's correlation test was used in this study for inference analysis. Pearson's correlation test was used to examine the relationship between spiritual intelligence variables and role stress. The results of the correlation analysis show that the correlation value is -0.232 ($r = .0232$), and the probability value is 0.015, which is tested at a significant level of 0.05. This probability value was smaller than the significant level ($p < 0.05$). This shows that spiritual intelligence has a negative relationship with role stress among indigenous school teachers.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings of this study indicate the relationship between spiritual intelligence in reducing the stress level of a teacher's role in an indigenous school. This situation proves that a teacher of high spiritual intelligence will be more satisfied, happy, and mentally harmonious. Therefore, the development of spiritual intelligence can be an important factor in improving teachers' quality of life and mental well-being.

The results of this study are also expected to provide meaningful guidance and insight to the respective authorities such as the Ministry of Education, Malaysia (MOE), the State Education Department (JPN), the District Education Office (PPD), and the school administration. This will facilitate everyone to understand the level of mental well-being of the teachers. In addition, this study's results can provide a fundamental concept for educational institutions to integrate an approach that focuses on the development of spiritual intelligence in teacher's professional development programs. Finally, this integrated approach will improve teacher's mental well-being and enrich the overall learning experience in schools.

As an added value to this study, it is suggested that in conducting future studies related to role stress, it should add in other variables; such as role distance, role erosion, role isolation, and personal absence, that have been studied and reviewed by other researchers, for example, a research by Sudeshna Basu Mukherjee (2015). Furthermore, it is also suggested to examine the variable of religious appreciation. This is based on the views and studies by Husni Mohd Radzi, Lilie Zahara Ramly, Sapora Sipon and Khatijah Othman (2014) as well as Siti Aishah Yahya and Sidar Nasrun (2016), who have agreed that religious appreciation factors can influence and have a direct relationship towards role stress.

Finally, based on the research that has been conducted, it was found that the level of role stress among indigenous school teachers is at a moderately high level. Even though it is only at a moderately high level, this does not mean that there is no role stress. Role stress still exists among teachers, but fortunately, the situation is under control and not worrying. However, if this condition is ignored and improperly managed, it could lead to a more severe implication.

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